

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

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Abbreviations list

AP	Application Profile
API	Application Programming Interface
DCS	RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMP-IF	Data Management Plan-Interoperability Framework
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
EOSC	European Open Science cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAIR-IF	FAIR Testing Interoperability Framework
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
IF	Interoperability Framework
IF/RA	Interoperability Framework/Reference Architecture
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation-Linked Data
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
UML	Unified Modelling Language
PID	Persistent Identifier
PTA	Plan-Track-Assess
RA	Reference Architecture
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RUP	Rational Unified Process
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graph-Interoperability Framework

Executive Summary

This deliverable introduces the OSTrails reference architecture along with three Interoperability Frameworks aligned with the project's pillars: Data Management Plans (DMPs), Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), and FAIR Assessment. The reference architecture provides guidance on realising interactions between key components identified in the OSTrails pathways – see *D1.1 Pathways*. It clarifies which interactions are standardised within the Interoperability Frameworks and which are relevant to the project without prescribing specific implementation methods. For example, while the reference architecture specifies when the DMP API (part of the DMP Interoperability Framework) must be used, it leaves the method of accessing information from data repositories flexible.

A key objective of this deliverable is to prevent vendor lock-in, ensuring tools and services can be used interchangeably in typical scenarios outlined by the pathways. For instance, any SKG conforming to the SKG-IF can seamlessly integrate with DMP tools to provide additional insights into reused datasets. This deliverable emphasises harmonising the modelling and exchange of information across research data management services while allowing diverse implementation choices tailored to specific use cases.

The architecture also supports both current well-known and potential future patterns of interactions between components, fostering innovative use cases that enhance automation and machine-actionability of digital object information exchange. For example, while it is yet uncommon for data repositories to update DMPs, the architecture anticipates and accommodates such potential pathways.

This deliverable is closely linked to *D2.5 – OSTrails Commons Specifications*, which details the individual components of the Interoperability Frameworks. It reflects the project's status as of month 12, with follow-up deliverables planned. These include a revised version incorporating feedback from pilots (month 30) and a deliverable on developed commons (month 24).

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Section 1 presents the methodology. Section 2 presents the architecture, the rationale behind it and examples of using it. The interoperability frameworks are presented in Sections 3, 4, and 5. Section 6 presents conclusions.

1. Methodology

This section presents the methodology for developing the OSTrails reference architecture and Interoperability Frameworks.

We follow the design science research paradigm [6] to develop and evaluate the reference architecture and all artifacts that are included within the interoperability frameworks. Specifically, we follow the three design science cycles:

- *Relevance cycle* that ensures the design solves real-world problems by aligning with stakeholder needs and system requirements. This is given by the scope of the project and by the composition of the consortium, which includes stakeholders from various domains and countries.
- *Design cycle* that focuses on an iterative process of designing, evaluating, and refining artifacts. In OSTrails we do this by working in a collaborative way and having regular meetings in which feedback from project members is regularly incorporated into the design of specific artifacts, such as, interfaces, models, architecture, frameworks, etc.
- *Rigor cycle* that ensures the design is based on sound theoretical foundations and uses existing knowledge or methods. We follow this cycle by collaborating with other EOSC-related projects and by following well-established standards within the respective communities; for example, we use OpenAPI specification for the design of APIs or UML diagrams to depict the reference architecture discussed in this deliverable.

The development of the reference architecture is also aligned with the TOGAF Standard, specifically with the Architecture Development Method for Information Systems.¹ Specifically, we followed the “nine steps”:

1. Select Reference Models, Viewpoints, and Tools
2. Develop Baseline Application Architecture Description
3. Develop Target Application Architecture Description
4. Perform Gap Analysis
5. Define Candidate Roadmap Components
6. Resolve Impacts Across the Architecture Landscape
7. Conduct Formal Stakeholder Review
8. Finalise the Application Architecture
9. Create the Architecture Definition Document

Steps 1 to 3 are covered by the multi-step consultation within the consortium to identify existing and expected interactions between tools and services. The consultation helped

¹ <https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/togaf92-doc/arch/>

us identify pathways, key architecture components, and requirements for the interoperability frameworks. The key steps of the consultation were:

- a) Describe existing tools and services – the goal was to get a better picture of how tools and services interact with each other, e.g. what information they consume and provide. To do so, each tool/service owner provided an informal sketch of his or her service focusing on the communication to the outside. The conceptual components of their services describe existing and expected integrations. We deliberately did not follow any formal representation language to make sure that participants were not limited by their expressivity. A list of conceptual components can be found in the M4 document [4].
- b) Create abstract representation of tools and services – we analysed the sketches created and grouped them into classes of tools and services based on similarities among them. This allowed us to abstract away from the specific tools and services which helped us to define a generic/universal component that is not specific to a particular tool or service. For example, most DMP tools connect to project/grant registries to get information on projects – hence the abstract representation includes such an interface. This became the basis for a more structured discussion on the interactions between tools and services and influenced the pathways, architecture, and interoperability frameworks.
- c) Define pathways – the pathways provide the process view, i.e. they tell how these components are used together to deliver value to stakeholders. In other words, pathways allow us to identify which component integrations are more common or have higher priority. For example, the pathways tell us how DMP tools are used with other components during research to get automated feedback on FAIRness and DMP quality. Deliverable D1.1 describes pathways in detail. The identified Pathways are depicted in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2**.
- d) Define initial architecture – a result of putting two layers on each other: pathways and underlying generic conceptual elements and the connections between them necessary to realise the pathway. This is presented in milestone document M4.
- e) Define initial interoperability frameworks - we identified existing standards and reviewed them in view of the needs identified by the consortium. We also reached out to other EOSC projects and communities like RDA to identify what is currently being developed outside of the project that we may rely on.

The fourth step (“Perform gap analysis”) is described in D2.1 Analysis of the OSTrails IF Tools Compliance [26]. D2.1 analyses in a systematic way 38 different tools used within the consortium and compares them against the initial drafts of the Interoperability Frameworks (IF). Furthermore, D2.1 provides sets of requirements for the design of DMP-IF, SKG-IF, and FAIR-IF.

We used the initial draft of the architecture and the interoperability frameworks to discuss their feasibility with tool, service, and use case owners. Specifically, we wanted to identify whether the proposed design addresses the expected standardisation needs, is relevant to pilot and cluster representatives, and whether the consortium has sufficient expertise and backing to make specific architectural decisions. We did this in several online meetings and through asynchronous communication channels. This covers steps 5-8.

This document represents step 9 of the TOGAF standard and presents and explains the rationale for the reference architecture and interoperability frameworks proposed.

Figure 1. Pathways – potential user actions triggered from different components. Source: deliverable D1.1.

2. Reference Architecture

In this section we present the reference architecture developed by the OSTrails project by discussing its components and showing the use of Interoperability Frameworks as its essential building blocks. We also provide basic definitions and explain how the reference architecture should be used to guide specific deployments, e.g. within pilots or by anyone who wants to become interoperable in the DMP, SKG, and FAIR assessment areas.

2.1. Definitions and design principles

To begin with, we provide a definition of the reference architecture and discuss the design principles that influenced the architecture presented in Section 2.3.

Reference Architecture - definition

- “A software reference architecture captures the basic building blocks and architectural design decisions of systems in a certain application or technology domain. From a software architecture perspective, reference architectures represent reusable architecture knowledge in the form of generic artifacts, standards, design guidelines, architectural styles, domain vocabulary, etc. [1]. Therefore, reference architectures help simplify the development of new systems and architectures in a particular domain. Furthermore, reference architectures facilitate standardisation and interoperability of systems within an application or technology domain: Systems within such domain can be designed based on the same reference architecture and therefore follow the same design guidelines, standards, and principles.” [2]
- “Reference architecture (...) provides a common vocabulary, reusable designs, and industry best practices that are used as a constraint for more concrete architectures. Typically, reference architecture includes common architecture principles, patterns, building blocks, and standards. They are not solution architectures (i.e., they are not implemented directly). (...) A reference architecture provides a template, often based on the generalisation of a set of solutions. These solutions may have been generalised and structured for the depiction of one or more architecture structures based on the harvesting of a set of patterns that have been observed in a number of successful implementations.” [3]

Based on the definitions provided in the box above, we can conclude that the reference architecture:

- **Is not an implementation blueprint** – it needs to be tailored each time to a specific deployment context. It does not prescribe the architecture of the actual system.
- **Is independent of a specific technology or service** – It does not mandate using specific systems or services. This decision has to be made for specific deployments.
- **Does not require all components to be instantiated** – the reference architecture is a summary of requirements as expressed through pathways. If certain pathways are not relevant in a given deployment context, then these parts of the architecture can be omitted without sacrificing interoperability, e.g. Integration of DMP Platforms with SKGs can be implemented without FAIR Testing.

Based on the points above, the ambition of the **OSTrails reference architecture is to be a projection of the work done to develop the Interoperability Framework and Commons² on the set of identified pathways**. By doing so, we make explicit which communications between conceptual services are subject to standardisation (by e.g. using APIs in the Interoperability Frameworks), and which of them are subject to individual judgment depending on a specific deployment context or a service (e.g. repositories that will still provide OAI-PMH or other interfaces) and are therefore out of scope for the Interoperability Frameworks.

The OSTrails reference architecture does not aim to depict all possible interactions in all possible settings. **Other uses of interoperability frameworks are possible but not mandated by the architecture**. For example, repositories may want to use the SKG API directly to provide access to their contents. This may be a valid decision in many settings, but the consortium of OSTrails does not make any statements on this, and for this reason, such use cases are not covered by the reference architecture.

It is important to note that both the underlying pathways as well as the reference architecture itself **describe both existing and possible future interactions between components**. Thus, they aim to facilitate novel use cases that increase automation and

² The **OSTrails Commons** are formally defined as a collection of open, reusable, and adaptable resources that collectively enable and enhance interoperability within the OSTrails ecosystem and beyond. These resources are designed to **lower adoption barriers** to integration by standardising interactions between tools, ensuring alignment with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework (IF) and Reference Architecture (RA). The Commons are **not standalone tools or services**; rather, they provide the **foundational elements that support and guide the development, operation, and evolution** of interoperable research-supporting platforms. For more information on Commons see **Deliverable D2.5 OSTrails Commons Specification**.

machine-actionability of information exchange for all types of digital objects. For example, it is not a current practice for data repositories to provide updates to DMPs, but the reference architectures take this into account as this is one of the identified pathways.

2.2. Notation used

The reference architecture is depicted using UML Component diagram. Such diagrams can be used to depict the relationships between different conceptual parts of systems, e.g. to show which components communicate with each other and what communication protocol is used for that purpose. UML Component diagrams are only one of the few possibilities to depict a system; they are often accompanied by other types of diagrams that focus on different aspects of the system. For example, in Section 2.4, we use an additional sequence diagram to represent the time ordering of the interaction between systems, but since the OSTrails reference architecture does not make a recommendation on this, we can restrict ourselves to the UML Component diagram. We also do not go into the details of individual components or interfaces, because this is either specific to a given deployment or regulated by the Interoperability Frameworks described in the subsequent chapter.

In the remainder of this section, we provide basic definitions of elements used in the reference architecture to establish a common language with the reader.

Table 1. Basic elements of the UML Component diagram.

SYMBOL	NAME	DESCRIPTION
	Component	Used to represent conceptual elements of the architecture, e.g. systems or services.
	Lollipop notation	Used to describe the connection between two components. The component connected to the circle offers the interface, and the other one consumes this interface.
	Lollipop notation simplified	In cases when there are many components using the same interface, we use the simplified notation. The location of the circle tells which component exposes the interface, i.e., the one that is closer to the circle.

Figure 3 shows a very basic example of the notation we use for the reference architecture. It shows that component A provides an interface that is accessed by component B. In the reference architecture, we use this notation to show that some service provides an API, and the other services communicate using this API. Please note that the diagram does NOT convey the opposite message, i.e. it is not true to say that

component A accesses information from component B. To depict this, we would need to add another lollipop connection flipped horizontally.

Figure 3. Basic example of UML notation used.

2.3. Reference Architecture Specification

This section presents and discusses the reference architecture specification. Please refer to the previous section for the definition and information on its scope and design decisions made. **Figure 4** presents the OSTrails reference architecture.

Figure 4. OSTrails Reference Architecture.

We use colour coding in the diagram:

- Orange represents the components and communications that are subject to standardisation within the DMP-IF.
- Blue represents the components and communications that are subject to standardisation within the SKG-IF.

- Green represents the components and communications that are subject to standardisation within the FAIR-IF.
- Gray represents the components and communications that are relevant for delivering the pathways identified by the project but are not subject to any of the interoperability frameworks, e.g. standards may already be in place, under development by other projects, or simply be based on custom interfaces provided by specific services.

The reference architecture consists of the following conceptual components:

- **DMP Platform** – Platform, tool, or service (software system) for planning data management, producing data management plans (DMPs), including machine-actionable data management plans (maDMPs).
- **SKG** - For the purposes of the OSTrails project, an SKG is defined as any database/repository with information pertaining to research products, processes and actors & agents which can present a graph-type view of this information via a suitable API.
- **FAIR Assessment Tool** – Software that applies a set of FAIR Tests to the metadata/data of a digital object (such as datasets), presents the output as a FAIR Test Result Set, and provides assistance on how to interpret and improve the results. FAIR Assessment tools may also include additional functionalities such as searching for and/or authoring Metrics and searching for and/or authoring Benchmarks.
- **DMP Evaluation Service** - A service that takes a DMP as input and gives as a result measurements indicating if the DMP meets given compliance requirements. These requirements depend on the evaluation scenario but in general consist of measurements for subsets of information contained in a DMP. Such measurements can be the FAIRness of digital objects included in the DMP, compliance of the DMP with the RDA maDMP standard, or automated measurements of funder requirements such as the existence of relevant information and their allowed values. To provide these measurements, the DMP Evaluator coordinates the inclusion of the results of other evaluators and resolves information contained in a DMP through SKGs and other sources.
- **Data Repository** – any service that stores and provides access to data. Usually, it provides a means for persistent identification and ensures that data is accompanied by metadata. Examples include zenodo.org, institutional repositories, etc.
- **Other SKG** – same definition as for the SKG. This element is introduced in the reference architecture to indicate that the SKG-IF can be used for communication between different SKGs.

The reference architecture says that a **DMP Platform** must provide a DMP API that can be used by other services. SKGs and data repositories use this API to interact with the DMP Platform. The specific operations of the API will be described elsewhere. For the time being, one can imagine that a data repository can use the DMP API to e.g. add information about a specific licence assigned to a dataset described by the DMP.

The **SKGs** must provide an SKG API so that other SKGs can interact with them. DMP Platforms use SKG API to access information in SKGs, e.g. to search for datasets, or to fetch information using identifiers. DMP Evaluation Service and FAIR assessment tools use the SKG API to get additional information needed during assessment. Data repositories also use this API.

FAIR Assessment Tools have APIs that are only partially defined by the OSTrails reference architecture; that is, while the input required by a FAIR assessment tool cannot be predicted, the output structures from all FAIR assessment tools (namely, the “FAIR Test Result Set” data structure) have been specified by the FAIR Reference Architecture (Deliverable D1.2). Further discussion regarding this appears in the chapter 5 of this document. DMP Platforms, DMP Evaluation Services, and SKGs can thus expect a standardised response when interacting with FAIR assessment tools that comply with the FAIR-IF.

The **DMP Evaluation Service** provides an interface that the DMP Platform uses to interact with it, i.e. send maDMPs for evaluation and fetch the results. This interface will be designed as part of the DMP Evaluation Service and described in a separate deliverable. Yet, it will be specific to this service and does not belong to any of the interoperability frameworks, i.e. in case other similar services exist, they can define their own interfaces.

In a similar way, **Data Repositories** may have custom APIs that are used by FAIR Assessment tools or DMP Platforms. OSTrails does not attempt to standardise this communication because it is already a subject of the work by the EOSC Future project on standardising access to content via PID [5].

2.4. Example of using the Reference Architecture

This section shows how the reference architecture can be used to guide the implementation of a specific use case. We provide an example to show how the reference architecture can be used in practice. The example is not exhaustive and do not aim to cover all possible implementations of the reference architecture.

Consider a scenario where a researcher publishes open-access data by uploading files and accompanying metadata to a designated repository. Metadata requirements often include cross-references to relevant publications, such as journal articles that utilize the data. Before publication, the repository operator conducts a FAIR assessment. This assessment verifies data quality and adherence to repository guidelines, providing feedback to the researcher for improvement. Upon successful publication, the Data Management Plan (DMP) is updated to reflect the final state of the data, including its location in the repository.

Figure 5 presents pathways identified by OSTrails. The connections highlighted in yellow are used in the example. **Figure 7** depicts a UML sequence diagram that depicts the interactions from the researcher and communication between components involved: data repository, FAIR Assessment Tool, DMP Platform, and SKG. The data repository invokes a series of actions to communicate with other components:

- SKG - to get information on cross-references, e.g. basic metadata of a journal paper for which the data is deposited into a repository.
- FAIR Assessment Tool – to test deposited data and metadata for FAIRness,
- DMP Platform – to send update to a DMP indicating that the data was published.

Figure 6 presents a UML Component diagram that is a subset of OSTrails Reference Architecture. It shows that communication between the data repository and other components is conducted with a use of Interoperability Frameworks: DMP-IF, SKG-IF, FAIR-IF.

Figure 5. Subset of pathways in the example of using reference architecture.

Figure 6. UML Component diagram depicting communication between components used in the example.

Figure 7. UML Sequence diagram used to depict interaction between components used in the example.

The reference architecture outlined in this section provides a structured approach to managing components and their interactions. This latest example illustrates its use through a specific use case. However, ensuring seamless integration and effective communication between these components requires a well-defined interoperability framework. An interoperability framework establishes the principles and standard

necessary to facilitate data exchange and functionality across the DMP platform, SKGs, FAIR Assessment tools and Data repositories. In the following sections, we will define interoperability frameworks for the DMP, SKG, and FAIR components.

3. DMP-IF

This chapter introduces the DMP Interoperability Framework (DMP-IF). We begin by clarifying the terminology, followed by an explanation of the framework's motivation. We then outline the relationships between the key elements of the DMP-IF. Additionally, we describe the target community and provide guidance on how to adopt the framework. In the subsequent sections, we provide details on each of the three key elements of the DMP-IF (see [Figure 8](#)):

- RDA DMP **common standard** for machine-actionable DMPs (DCS),
- OSTrails **application profile** for maDMPs,
- maDMP Application Programming Interface (**API**).

Definitions

- “**Interoperability** - (...) ability of organisations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organisations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems” [24]
- “The **European Interoperability Framework** (...) defines basic interoperability guidelines in the form of common principles, models and recommendations.” [24]
- “EOSC **Interoperability Framework** (IF) is structured according to the four interoperability layers already identified by the European Interoperability Framework: technical, semantic, organisational and legal.” [25]

Building on the definitions presented above, an **interoperability framework** refers to a set of guidelines, standards, and protocols that ensure the ability of different systems, applications, or organizations to work together effectively, exchanging data and functions seamlessly despite differences in their underlying technologies. The framework typically addresses the technical, semantic, and organizational aspects needed to facilitate collaboration and integration between disparate systems.

The DMP-IF follows this definition and is designed with DMP Platforms in mind but can be used by any service or tool that exchanges maDMPs. The IF does not prescribe internal organisation of services, e.g. their architecture or how they represent information internally. The IF focuses on how the information is exchanged with other services, i.e. defines concepts and models to represent the information, as well as actions that can be performed to get or modify information in a service implementing the DMP-IF. For example, listing all datasets described by a DMP, including their identifiers and licences, is performed in a unified way, independent of the underlying implementation. The DMP-IF addresses the technical and semantic layers only.

Figure 8. DMP-IF consists of elements building on top of each other.

The **common standard** is an RDA recommendation [12]. It defines a minimum set of concepts used to model information in DMPs common for most use cases. The **application profile** builds on top of the common standard. It provides additional concepts and constraints necessary to support the interactions identified in the pathways and reference architecture. Thus, it provides more concepts and more constraints that reflect the needs of OSTrails as whole and eventually EOSC. While both focus on establishing a common language on how information contained in DMPs is expressed in a machine-actionable way, the **API** provides a set of methods that can be used to perform specific actions on DMPs. The structure of messages exchanged with the use of the API is based on the common language defined by the common standard and the application profile.

The DMP-IF is **relevant to software engineers and service operators** who want to standardise how information on DMPs is exchanged. End-users, i.e. researchers, are not supposed to be aware of the DMP-IF. The DMP-IF facilitates the reuse and exchange of information so that typical RDM tasks can be automated, and DMPs are a place where all the information relevant to data management, e.g. type of data, storage location, access permissions, etc., are kept. DMP platforms should thus become a source of up-to-date information for other services that depend on them, e.g. researchers involved in a project described by a DMP should automatically get access to relevant equipment and repositories described by the DMP. As a result, creating the DMP should primarily benefit researchers by facilitating data management of their typical tasks and become less a one-time exercise to meet formal requirements.

Adopting the DMP-IF can be performed gradually and tailored to the needs of the specific use case. Yet, full interoperability can only be achieved when the specific service implements the complete maDMP API. This is because the API reflects the community

agreement on the common language used to describe the DMP contents and makes technical decisions that leave less room for interpretation, e.g. choice of communication protocol, such as HTTP, and ways to serialise the exchanged messages, for instance, using JSON.

3.1. RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs

This section presents the RDA DMP Common Standards for maDMPs (DCS) which is the basis on which the DMP-IF is built. We describe its structure and design assumptions. We also discuss its limitations to provide motivation for other DMP-IF elements developed in OSTrails.

Existing work

The DCS is an official recommendation of RDA. It provides a common set of concepts agreed upon by a broad community to represent traditional DMPs. It models information instead of questionnaires and hence makes the information machine-actionable. RDM services can expose DMP contents following the DCS to allow others to reuse information. The recommendation is intended to cover a wide range of use cases and does not set any funder specific requirements. For instance, the specification keeps it open whether a DMP is related to a project and whether this project is funded. Furthermore, the DCS represents information over the whole DMP lifecycle.

Figure 9 presents the concepts used in the DCS. Each concept can be further broken down into specific fields (not depicted). **Figure 10** shows an excerpt from the DCS. It shows sub-properties of the “contact” concept. For each of the sub-properties, the DCS provides a description, data type, cardinality, and an example. The DCS does not mandate any specific serialization format, e.g. JSON, XML, JSON-LD, etc. Yet, due to the demand from the community, the DCS is accompanied by JSON examples and JSON Schema as an ontology. The full specification can be found online [15]. More information on the development of the DCS can be found in [8], [13], [14].

OSTrails analysed DMP Platforms with respect to DCS compliance. This is described in D2.1. Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework tools compliance [26]. The key findings are: **“The DMP platforms that performed the per-tool analysis are committed to RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs.** All these tools support the import and export of the JSON representation at least partly or with respect to the internal representation of a DMP, i.e., what the users can provide in the specific platform. DSW also supports an RDF representation (together with JSON as a standalone document template). RDMO has an additional plugin for maDMP export. DMPTuuli has the same maDMP-capabilities as DMPRoadmap. Although DMP-related information is captured

and stored differently within each platform, it can be presented using a similar or even the same format and structure. This is valid not only for presenting, i.e., exporting but also for getting the DMP-related information into the platforms, i.e., importing. In their real usage, DMPs are employed for more actions, including partial import, change of settings and sharing, versioning, etc. These other tasks are currently done differently in different tools, as they are related to the internal data structures only without any standardization.”

Figure 9. Overview of the core concepts used in the RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs. Source: <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>

Properties in 'contact'

Name	Description	Data Type	Cardinality	Example Value
contact_id	Identifier for a contact person	Nested Data Structure	1	
mbox	E-mail address	String	1	cc@example.com
name	Name of the contact person	String	1	Charlie Chaplin

Figure 10. Excerpt from RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs. It shows sub-properties of the contact.

Ongoing and planned work

Together with the RDA DMP Common Standards WG we perform the maintenance of the recommendation. Tomasz Miksa and Marek Suchánek are co-chairs of the group, which facilitates the collaboration between the OSTrails and the RDA working group. To maintain the recommendation, we asked the community of users to provide comments and suggestions on the existing recommendation. They used the issues mechanism of GitHub where the recommendation is hosted. **Figure 11** provides the most recent issues submitted during the consultation. We are currently reviewing the submitted issues.

The RDA DMP Common Standards working group will be able to accept only minor and small changes to the recommendation. These will be mostly refinements bringing clarity or changes that are backward-compatible. As a result, we will have a stable and up-to-date set of concepts shared across the whole DMP community. Any major changes that could considerably influence the design of the recommendation need to be performed by a new working group – this is an RDA requirement. For this reason, OSTrails will develop the OSTrails application profile to incorporate bigger changes that also cover the project-specific needs, which may not be shared across the whole RDA community. This is described in the next section.

27 Open ✓ 26 Closed

Author ▾ Label ▾ Projects ▾ Milestones ▾ Assignee ▾ Sort ▾

- Renaming "project" to "grant" to match the SKG IF data model**
#84 opened 3 weeks ago by oana-dragomir 1
- Metadata standard identifier**
#83 opened 3 weeks ago by JacquemotMC
- ORCID or ORCID iD ?**
#82 opened 3 weeks ago by JacquemotMC
- Definitions examples**
#81 opened 3 weeks ago by JacquemotMC
- Cardinalities**
#80 opened 3 weeks ago by JacquemotMC
- Host identification**
#79 opened 3 weeks ago by JacquemotMC
- Clarification on URI Data Type**
#78 opened 3 weeks ago by ValentinFutterer
- Differences between RDA-DMP-Standard and RDMO-DMP-Standard**
#77 opened last month by Sabine-Schoenau
- preservation_statement in dataset is insufficiently described**
#75 opened on Oct 29, 2024 by steinbeck 1
- Currency Code**
#74 opened on Sep 29, 2024 by mahablue

Figure 11. Maintenance of the DCS – issues submitted by the community.

3.2. OSTrails Application Profile

This section presents the OSTrails application profile built on top of the DCS described in the previous section. We provide here a definition of the application profile and discuss its role within the DMP-IF.

The common standard provides basic interoperability between systems producing or consuming maDMPs. It foresees that further concepts can be added if needed, for example, to support domain-specific or funder-specific needs. The common standard itself is an application profile that builds on top of other standards such as Dublin Core or DCAT – see **Figure 12**. To support the discussion, we share below the definition of an application profile.

Application Profile (*definition*)

- “An application profile is a metadata design specification that uses a selection of terms from multiple metadata vocabularies, with added constraints, to meet application-specific requirements.”³
- “An application profile (AP) describes how a standard is to be applied in a particular domain or application. Standards typically do not contain constraints such as cardinality; these constraints are defined in the application profile. An application profile only applies to a specified domain. For example: The DCAT-AP is an application profile that specifies how the DCAT standard is to be used in the context of European data portals. An application profile must be accompanied by explanatory documentation.”⁴

The OSTrails application profile will extend the common standard by:

- adding new concepts
 - to increase coverage of funder requirements,
 - to reflect common needs identified by pilots in WP4,
 - to facilitate automated evaluation of DMPs and to incorporate results produced by FAIR assessment tools in WP3,
- introducing constraints to make certain fields mandatory,
- agreeing on specific vocabularies to be used instead of open text fields.

³ https://www.dublincore.org/resources/glossary/application_profile/

⁴ <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/application-profiles>

By defining one application profile, we want to mitigate a situation when every use case owner defines their own set of extensions. For example, we will define a set of concepts that support the requirements of most funders instead of having extensions per funder. This should prevent situations in which overlapping concepts are represented differently, and hence, the interoperability is lower. **Table 2** presents an example of fields that we already identified as necessary to become part of the OSTrails application profile that reflect common funder needs. Yet, there will still be cases when custom extensions to the OSTrails application profile may be necessary. These can be made on top – as indicated by the three dots in **Figure 12** – but they will not be part of the DMP-IF.

While the DCS is an official recommendation of RDA and must leave many decisions open, e.g., which type of controlled vocabulary to use for identifier types, the OSTrails application profile imposes additional constraints on the RDA recommendation that are relevant within the OSTrails and EOSC contexts. For example, the application profile may have stricter requirements regarding the use of persistent identifiers (rather than URLs) or may require the use of specific controlled vocabularies.

Figure 12. OSTrails application profile builds on top of other standards.

Table 2. Examples of concepts that may become part of the OSTrails AP that reflect common funder needs.

Name	Description	Data Type	Cardinality	Example Value
is_reused	To explicitly indicate whether the dataset is reused or was produced in the course of research. Allowed values are: reused, produced.	Term from Controlled Vocabulary	1	reused
target_audience	To state for whom this dataset can be relevant.	String	0..n	This dataset is of special interest to ethnomusicologists working on...
methodology	To describe methodology, procedures, workflows, etc. on how the dataset is created, can be recovered, ...	Nested Data Structure	0..n	This data is a result of simulation made using...

3.3. maDMP API

This section describes the third key element of the DMP-IF which is the maDMP Application Programming Interface (maDMP API). We provide motivation and outline key design challenges. The following are key definitions provided to support the description.

API (definition)

- “API stands for Application Programming Interface. In the context of APIs, the word Application refers to any software with a distinct function. Interface can be thought of as a contract of service between two applications. This contract defines how the two communicate with each other using requests and responses. Their API documentation contains information on how developers are to structure those requests and responses.”⁵

OpenAPI (definition)

- “The OpenAPI Specification (OAS) provides a consistent means to carry information through each stage of the API lifecycle. It is a specification language for HTTP APIs that defines structure and syntax in a way that is not wedded to the programming language the API is created in. API specifications are typically written in YAML or JSON, allowing for easy sharing and consumption of the specification. (...) APIs can be described in agnostic terms, decoupling them from any specific programming language. Consumers of your API specification do not need to understand the guts of your application or try to learn Lisp or Haskell if that’s what you chose to write it in. They can understand exactly what they need from your API specification, written in a simple and expressive language.”⁶

The RDA DMP Common Standard (DCS) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) has been adopted by most DMP tool providers to facilitate the import and export of maDMPs – see Deliverable D2.1 [26] and [10]. While this implementation represents a critical and necessary feature, it predominantly supports unidirectional data flow rather than enabling continuous and dynamic information exchange across various RDM services. An enterprise architecture has been proposed where maDMPs serve as connectors between services, enabling the automation of RDM tasks [9]. However, these integrations typically occur on a service-to-service basis and often require custom adaptations [11], which are both time-intensive and resource-demanding.

In OSTrails, we develop the maDMP API to address these challenges by introducing formal requirements encapsulated within a technical specification that adheres to the OpenAPI standard (see the definition above). This API framework specifies a standardised set of operations that can be executed on a DMP hosted by a service implementing the maDMP API. These operations encompass both read and write functionalities. For example, external services can retrieve information about datasets described in a DMP or update

⁵<https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/api/#:~:text=API%20stands%20for%20Application%20Programming,of%20service%20between%20two%20applications>

⁶ <https://www.openapis.org/what-is-openapi>

specific DMP fields based on actions performed in other systems. An illustrative use case involves the automatic addition of licensing information to a DMP when a dataset is published under a CC-BY licence in a data repository.

The broader objectives of the maDMP API are as follows:

- **Enable interoperability and interchangeability of DMP platforms:** Ensure that any DMP tool can be utilised in diverse contexts without compatibility concerns.
- **Reduce reliance on static text documents:** Shift away from narrative DMP formats, such as PDFs, towards enhanced use of persistent identifiers where appropriate.
- **Promote the reuse of information from DMPs:** Facilitate the transfer of information from DMPs to inform and drive actions within other RDM systems.
- **Enhance the quality and timeliness of DMPs:** Improve accuracy by sourcing data directly from systems where RDM activities are conducted.

This approach aims to establish a robust framework for seamless integration and automation in the RDM ecosystem, significantly advancing the utility and efficiency of DMPs. **The maDMP API does not replace existing APIs offered by DMP Platforms.** There are still operations that are specific to each platform. The maDMP API standardises typical interactions with maDMPs in a similar fashion as the DCS, which represents consensus on most common DMP elements in most settings, but not all of them.

We are developing the API iteratively, considering requirements and insights from:

- D1.1 Pathways,
- D2.1 Analysis of the OSTrails IF Tools Compliance, and
- progress in other components of the DMP-IF, including maintaining the DCS and developing the OSTrails Application Profile.

We are also actively prototyping. As part of this effort, we developed a prototypical service that simulates updates between a repository and a DMP tool. This prototype helps us explore and address challenges related to the maDMPs and the RDM lifecycle. **Figure 13** shows an early prototype of the maDMP API, represented through an OpenAPI specification. It includes two *PUT* methods for modifying information in the DMP and one *GET* method for retrieving the DMP. The figure provides detailed information for one of the *PUT* methods, including its description, parameters, and a sample message body sent to the */maDMP/object/identifier* endpoint.

Our initial findings highlight two key challenges that we must address in the API design:

1. Authorization and Authentication - The definition of who can execute specific methods and under what conditions is crucial. For example, not all users should have full access to the DMP, nor have permission to modify every section of it.

2. Evolving Identifiers - As data traverses systems throughout its lifecycle, the assumption of persistent identifiers assigned at the outset cannot be made. The API must be capable of handling changing identifiers to effectively track dataset evolution.

We describe these challenges and the prototype design in [7]. We are using the lessons learned from this prototype to guide further iterations of the maDMP API. To advance this work, we are collaborating with the broader RDA community. We are establishing a new RDA working group to involve a larger community of DMP tool stakeholders in defining the API. Our application to the RDA Tiger project for support in organizing this working group received positive feedback.

PUT /madmp Modify maDMP information

GET /madmp Get the maDMP

PUT /madmp/object/identifier Modify the maDMP object identifier

This access point is used to change the object identifier of the maDMP. It is necessary to send the mandatory maDMP values as a parameter and values for the identifier changes in the body. The change is made only if the RDM service has the right to change the specific identifier. Only changeable identifiers can be modified.

Parameters

Name	Description
identifier * required string (query)	The maDMP property DMP identifier Example : https://doi.org/10.1371/123
created * required string(\$date-time) (query)	The maDMP property created using the relevant ISO 8601 Date and Time compliant string Example : 2022-02-23T09:01:57
modified * required string(\$date-time) (query)	The maDMP property modified using the relevant ISO 8601 Date and Time compliant string Example : 2022-02-23T10:01:57

Request body application/json

Scheme for changing the identifier

Example Value | Schema

```
{
  "atLocation": "/DMP-23/Dataset-1",
  "specializationOf": "dataset:identifier",
  "value": "hdl.handle.net/11353/10.923628"
}
```

Figure 13. An early prototype of the maDMP API in the form of the OpenAPI specification.

4. SKG-IF

With the DMP Interoperability Framework defined, this chapter introduces the Scientific/Scholarly Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF). It outlines its motivation, relation to key elements, and applications in OSTrails. Subsequently, it provides details on each of the three main components of SKG-IF: the SKG-IF Data Model, SKG-IF Data Model Extensions, and the SKG-IF Common API.

The SKG-IF data model [16] is designed to enhance interoperability among different knowledge graph systems and platforms used in research. It facilitates the exchange and use of data across these systems by defining a shared language and standardised operations. Researchers or end-users are not expected to interact directly with the SKG-IF. Instead, it enables automated workflows and interoperability between services, enhancing the research ecosystem's efficiency and machine-actionability.

OSTrails SKG-IF is based on the RDA SKG interoperability framework. By providing a standardised approach to modelling a core set of scholarly data, the SKG-IF supports diverse applications involving compatible SKGs, such as combining SKGs to build new ones or exchanging data between SKGs to benefit from each other's construction methods. OSTrails will extend the existing RDA model of SKGs, propose (a mechanism for) model extensions and an API that can be used to enable scientific discovery and assessment. The OSTrails project will do so in the context of, or in close collaboration with, the RDA SKG-IF WG adding a scientific perspective to the previous scholarly one.

More specifically, SKG-IF data model entities are currently described with a comprehensive set of metadata properties, initially agreed on by the existing SKG community of stakeholders (DataCite, OpenCitation, Crossref, OpenAlex, OpenAIRE Graph), inspired also by existing metadata standards or best practices such as EuroCRIS/CERIF and now the perspective of the scientific communities. The model is agnostic of specific PID schemes or vocabularies, enabling cross-SKG interoperability by agreeing on a common structure and sharing of specific semantics. When PIDs or vocabularies are requested (e.g. resource types), properties require the vocabulary name and the specific value. Finally, the IF adopts JSON-LD, a widely recognised data exchange standard, to ensure seamless data exchange and semantic interoperability.⁷

The work on SKG-IF is performed in the context of RDA, guaranteeing a broad set of stakeholders taking part in the decision making. OSTrails brings to the Working Group the requirements arising by scientific communities and service providers in achieving the project objectives. The project roadmap may, therefore, potentially not always be synced and aligned with the RDA WG's. To this aim, as described below, in its first year OSTrails

⁷ JSON-LD, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8f9bbb>

has co-designed and strongly contributed to the definition of *SKG-IF extensions*. Extensions are a mechanism allowing a community to define “customizations” of the SKG-IF core model, such as new entities, new properties of existing entities, or new relationships. Extensions, today part of the SKG-IF framework, can compensate the difference in rhythm, when manifesting, between an RDA WG and project objectives, which are driven by deadlines and deliverables. Starting from interoperability use-cases identified in the project, OSTrails partners have identified (i) which entities of the SKG data model can be adopted to meet their requirements and, when such entities are missing, (ii) the SKG extensions required to fulfil them.

4.1. SKG-IF Data Model

The SKG-IF Data Model provides a baseline model for scholarly knowledge graphs, supporting core entities like:

- **Research Products:** Publications, datasets, software.
- **Agents:** Authors, institutions, organizations.
- **Grants:** Funding information linked to research outputs.
- **Data Sources:** Repositories and registries providing access to research outputs.
- **Venues:** Publishing gateways, e.g. journals, dataset repositories.
- **Topics:** Keywords or themes describing research content.
- **Relationships:** Links between entities, such as *cites*, *isAuthoredBy*, *isFundedBy*.

The framework aligns with existing metadata practices, such as Dublin Core and DCAT, while remaining agnostic of specific value types or vocabulary choices, as these may vary and depend on the individual SKG domains. JSON-LD is used as the data exchange format, ensuring consistency and semantic interoperability across systems.

OSTrails ensures that when sharing data about these entities, its tools adhere to SKG-IF's formats, enabling seamless integration across services.

4.2. SKG-IF data model extensions

The first contribution of OSTrails to the SKG WG is the co-design of the mechanism of *extensions*. Extensions make the SKG-IF inherently extensible, allowing domain-specific or community-driven customizations of the data model by inclusion of new entities, attributes to existing entities, or relationships beyond the SKG-IF core model.

The current SKG-IF proposal and model provide a robust foundation for SKG interoperability across diverse scientific domains, by focusing on scholarly communication commons, hence on bibliographic metadata of published research products. As a start, the RDA WG focused on the common entities (as listed above) among known WG members, namely Crossref, DataCite, CERIF, OpenCitations, OpenAlex,

ResearchGraph.org, and OpenAIRE Graph. Still, many other entities are to be added incrementally to the core model, to cover for more specific research workflow aspects and other less common but growingly important scenarios. Moreover, when shifting into specific scientific domains, several aspects remain underrepresented or entirely absent, which limits the framework's ability to fully support diverse research outputs and contexts. Specifically, starting from OSTrails use-cases, we have identified the following urgent gaps:

1. **Underrepresented Core Entities:** Instruments (e.g., telescopes, spectrometers) and services (e.g., data repositories, computational platforms, data processing services) are critical components in many research workflows but are not currently modelled.
2. **Provenance:** While traceability is crucial for assessing reliability and quality of scholarly data, the current model does not adequately address provenance attributes, such as data sources from which metadata was collected or methods that inferred attribute values.
3. **Specialised Metadata:** Fields specific to application-level requirements, such as metrics for FAIRness, data quality, or licensing, are not fully defined.
4. **Scientific domain entities:** entity profiles describing entities at the discipline level, e.g. atmospheric data.
5. **Relationships:** More nuanced relationships (e.g., `isValidatedBy`, `isTestedOn`) are required to describe complex interactions between entities.

As anticipated, the SKG-IF, with the contribution of OSTrails partners, has been endowed with the *extensions* mechanism,⁸ with the purpose of making the framework flexible and extendable by design, allowing it to adapt to new entity types and metadata specific to certain domains or organisations.

Extensions ensure the model's utility over time as scholarly/scientific practices and technologies evolve. They offer a powerful mechanism to address gaps in the current SKG-IF model, enabling it to evolve alongside the diverse and dynamic needs of the research community. By introducing domain-specific entities, attributes, and relationships, extensions ensure the framework remains relevant across various scientific disciplines without overcomplicating its core structure. They enhance interoperability by accommodating specialised metadata, such as provenance, metrics for FAIRness, and licensing details, which are essential for improving traceability and trust in scholarly data. Moreover, extensions provide the flexibility to incorporate nuanced relationships, such as linking instruments to datasets or test results to protocols, fostering a richer and more comprehensive representation of research workflows. This ensures that the SKG-IF

⁸ <https://skg-if.github.io/extensions>

remains a robust and scalable framework, capable of supporting both current practices and future advancements in scholarly knowledge management.

4.3. Entities Available in SKGs

Based on data collected for D2.1, these are the entities and relationships identified in SKGs mapped to the SKG-IF:

Table 3: Entities & relationships available in SKG IF

ENTITY	DESCRIPTION	SKG-IF MAPPING	REFS	CORE MODEL
<i>Publications</i>	Scholarly articles, papers, and reports (includes DMPs)	Research Product	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes
<i>Authors</i>	Individuals contributing to research outputs.	Agent	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#agent	Yes
<i>Institutions</i>	Universities, research centres, and affiliated organisations	Agent	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#agent	Yes
<i>Research Data</i>	Datasets generated or (re)used in research	Research Product	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes
<i>Projects</i>	Research initiatives, grants, or collaborative efforts	Grant + associated relationships	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#grant	Yes
<i>Funding Bodies</i>	Organisations supporting research financially.	Agent	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#agent	Yes
<i>Keywords/Topics</i>	Themes or subjects of research	Topic	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#topic	Yes
<i>Citations</i>	References connecting scholarly works	Relationship between Research Products	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes

<i>Conferences</i>	Events for presenting and disseminating research findings	Venue	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#venue	Yes
<i>Patents</i>	Intellectual property arising from research	Research Product	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes
<i>Instruments</i>	Hardware or tools used for data collection and experimentation	None		Candidate to be
<i>Services</i>	Agent available via APIs or Web, in support of science	When service is a data source, can map to Data Source. When service is a publishing gateway e.g. data catalogue, it can be mapped to "Venue"	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#data-source https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#venue	Candidate to be
<i>Software</i>	Tools and applications developed or utilised during research activities	Research Product	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes
<i>Protocols</i>	Methodologies or procedures standardised for reproducibility	Research Product	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes
<i>Peer Reviews</i>	Evaluations of research outputs ensuring quality	Research Product	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes
<i>Licenses</i>	Legal permissions defining how research outputs can be used	Properties of Research Product	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/#research-product	Yes
<i>Standards</i>	Guidelines or frameworks ensuring uniformity (e.g., metadata standards)		https://fairsharing.org/API_doc	Candidate to be

<i>Identifiers</i>	Persistent or local identifiers (e.g., DOIs, ORCID, RAiD) for entities	Properties for various entities	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/	Yes
<i>Metrics</i>	Measures of quality, FAIRness, impact, or usage of research outputs	Properties for various entities	https://skg-if.github.io/data-model/	Yes
<i>Test Results</i>	Outcomes from FAIR assessments, quality evaluations, or reproducibility checks		https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/persistent-identification-instruments-wg/activity/	To be discussed

SKG core extension: new entity instruments

One example is the *Instruments* extension, which introduces entities representing tools and hardware used in fields like physics, biology, and environmental sciences. Examples can be telescopes, sensors, microscopes, etc. An initial example of how such a metadata profile could look like is depicted below. OSTrails will consult and collaborate with existing initiatives working on modelling instruments, in order to avoid redundancy and maximise the benefit for the scientific community.

Properties:

- **InstrumentType:** Use specific terms for the instrument's category, e.g., 'analytical' or 'observational.'
- **ModelVersion:** Include model names and versions as structured data fields.
- **Affiliation:** Specify the lab, institution, or research group related to the instrument.
- **Provenance:** Track the instrument's origin and history, specifying the manufacturer and past usage.

SKG core extension: new entity properties modelling *provenance*

Definition: A *Provenance* extension is important to disambiguate the source of each piece of metadata for an SKG entity and, in some cases, at the field level. Provenance extension

has been proposed.⁹ Further discussion is expected in project due course, considering standard provenance models¹⁰ and approaches across existing SKGs and data services.

4.4. SKG-IF Common API

The SKG-IF introduces an API for lookup/direct access, whose aim is to return an entry record given its identifier. In OSTrails, inspired by the thematic clusters, several compelling use cases were outlined showcasing how the interoperability framework could be enhanced with search APIs enabling discovery across SKGs. Below are the summarised use cases:

1. **DMP Tool Search Dataset:** Allows Data Management Plan (DMP) tool users at ESRF to search datasets using free-text queries, retrieving relevant datasets through the SKG-IF API. This use case streamlines dataset selection in DMPs, highlighting its search capabilities across different repositories.
2. **SKG to Other SKGs (CLARIN, SSHOMP Pilots):** Facilitates information exchange and linking datasets, persons, or tools with persistent identifiers (PIDs) across SKGs (e.g., SSHOMP, CESSDA, OpenAIRE), enriching user navigation by pulling related core entities in one API call, thus enhancing cross-SKG connectivity.
3. **Discovery and Alignment Based on Semantic Context Without PIDs:** Supports finding related datasets based on semantic similarity or shared descriptive attributes when PIDs are unavailable. Semantic search and graph-based exploration replace PID-dependent queries to reveal connections via keywords, themes, or affiliations.
4. **Track Dissemination Based on Metadata Evolution and Entity Versions:** Tracks where and how metadata associated with an item change over time across SKGs. This use case focuses on metadata versioning, provenance comparison, highlighting discrepancies using the PID as a consistent anchor.
5. **Track Data Usage on Publications (CESSDA Pilot):** Enables CESSDA to enhance research data metadata by identifying related publications that cite the data. This integration searches SKGs for "related_product" types and links them via identifiers, enriching data-publication connections.
6. **Explore / Identify Subgraph (OEAW):** Allows the extraction of relevant subgraphs in an SKG for analysis or alignment. It employs search parameters like author, country, and discipline, enabling users to filter and explore datasets, software, and resources efficiently.

⁹ <https://github.com/skg-if/extensions/issues/4>, originally discussed at <https://github.com/skg-if/interoperability-framework/issues/15>

¹⁰ PROV, <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm>

7. **Retrieve Records from the SKG to Fill DMP Fields (SOCIB):** Utilises the organizational SKG to automate the completion of DMP fields, aiding in marine data collection planning. Queries provide dropdown options for names, grants, while integrating external sources for project data when necessary.

Such use-cases serve as user requirements for the definition of a standard search API for the SKG-IF WG. From the use cases, the following generic operators can be identified:

1. **Search and Filter Operators:**
 - a. **Keyword Search:** Enable free-text search within titles, abstracts, or full-text metadata.
 - b. **Exact Match:** Retrieve records matching an exact phrase or term.
 - c. **Field-specific Filters:** Apply criteria to specific metadata fields such as author, publication year, institution, and resource type.
2. **Logical Operators:**
 - a. **AND, OR, NOT:** Combine multiple conditions to refine search queries.
 - b. **Nesting:** Use parentheses to control the precedence of logical operators.
3. **Relational Operators:**
 - a. **Equality/Inequality:** Filter records based on exact or non-exact matches (e.g., greater than, less than).
 - b. **Range Queries:** Specify numerical or date ranges to filter search results (e.g., publication dates).
4. **Semantic Operators:**
 - a. **Similarity Search:** Identify records with semantic similarity based on keywords or attributes.
 - b. **Ontology-based Filtering:** Use controlled vocabularies or ontologies to refine results by semantic categories.
5. **Aggregation and Grouping Operators:**
 - a. **Count, Sum, Average:** Perform statistical operations on metadata fields.
 - b. **Group By:** Aggregate records by specific fields, such as author or institution.
6. **Graph Traversal Operators:**
 - a. **Pathfinding:** Discover relationships between entities by traversing the graph.
 - b. **Subgraph Extraction:** Select and retrieve connected subsets of the graph based on criteria.
7. **Sorting and Pagination:**
 - a. **Sort By:** Order results by specified fields, such as relevance, alphabetical order, or date.
 - b. **Pagination:** Manage large result sets by dividing them into pages with limit and offset parameters.
8. **Versioning and Provenance Operators:**

- a. **Version Tracking:** Retrieve historical versions of metadata entries.
- b. **Provenance Queries:** Access metadata about the origin and changes of records.

This set of operators brings up a mix of traditional keyword queries, a-la Google, and graph-like path queries, a-la RDF. These may be efficiently supported depending on the kind of back-end database (full-text index, triple store) and can of course be inefficiently/partly supported by inappropriate back-ends (path-queries in full-text indexes). OSTrails partners prioritised a pragmatic solution by addressing keyword search and optionally a set of drill-down queries. This decision was strengthened by an analysis conducted of existing APIs from known SKGs, which seemed to suggest this as the most common approach to accessing SKGs. In particular, we have identified the following generic design principles, which we intend to respect in the design phase:

1. Support search by entity type and fields.
2. Define an API syntax/template that enables smooth adaptation to any SKG-IF extension.
3. Provide JSON-LD compatible responses, identifying contexts for all entities and API result sets (header and body of the records).
4. Responses will be research product centric, meaning that product record will embed outgoing relationships to records of related entities (e.g. agents, references, etc.).
5. Convenience filters can be optionally provided to support queries that touch upon combination of entities based in their relationships, e.g. "return publication that are related with at least 3 datasets".

The plan is to release first specification and implementation of the SKG-IF APIs by June 2025. The extent and coverage of the use-cases by the specification is to be discussed, as well as the extent of operators initially implemented by the OSTrails SKG providers.

5. FAIR-IF

Having established the DMP-IF and SKG-IF, we now present the FAIR Interoperability Framework (FAIR-IF). The FAIR-IF, and the description of it in this section, is distinct from the other IFs covered in this document. Notably, FAIR assessment tools are numerous (e.g., FAIR Evaluator,¹¹ FOOPS! [17],¹² FAIROs [18],¹³ F-UJI [19],¹⁴ O’Faire [20],¹⁵ FAIR checker [21],¹⁶ with a list of the 30 known FAIR assessment platforms available at the [FAIR Assist website](#)); most have existed for several years; and while they execute different tests using different metrics, the automated platforms largely function in the same way - that is:

- The assessment tool, and/or its component tests, have APIs defined by an OpenAPI interface descriptor.
- They consume the identifier of the digital object that needs to be tested.
- A set of tests is selected.
- The tests are run over metadata extracted from an exploration of the digital object and any of its metadata references.
- A test assessment report is output, often accompanied by a visualisation.

Hence, unlike the other IFs described in this document, the creation of the FAIR-IF required very little development from scratch. Moreover, the long history of FAIR testing, and the convergence of most assessment tools toward a near-identical approach, reduced the need for input from the OSTrails Pilots with respect to designing interoperability behaviours (the Pilots are, however, extensively contributing to our definition of novel testing benchmarks). The primary development activity (related to the *interoperability* of the FAIR component) has been focused on defining a common format for test assessment outputs that ensures consistent naming and a common test report schema such that the outputs from the numerous existing tools can be compared to one another (the primary objective of the FAIR-IF).

Considerably more attention has been paid to the internal representations of, for example, metrics, benchmarks, and tests, within the FAIR assessment tools. Generally, these are not exposed to other components of the OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture, and they are primarily used to describe, discover, and allow comparisons

¹¹ <https://w3id.org/AmlFAIR>

¹² <https://w3id.org/foops/>

¹³ <https://w3id.org/FAIROS/api>

¹⁴ <https://f-uji.net/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/agroportal/fairness>

¹⁶ <https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/>

between FAIR tests among the various assessment tools. These internal components of the FAIR-IF use, almost exclusively, existing standards or extensions of standards such as the W3C Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) [22]¹⁷ and the W3C Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV) [23].¹⁸ **They are described in a dedicated deliverable (Deliverable D1.2 - FAIR Reference Model)** where there is a detailed discussion of the requirements for a shared model for test descriptors – particularly with respect to their registration and discoverability - and the decisions made to that end. Because these are largely tangential to the *interoperability* of the FAIR-IF component of the OSTrails Interoperability Architecture, those details will only be superficially discussed here, and thus this description of the FAIR-IF component will be abbreviated compared to the other IF components in this document.

5.1. FAIR-IF Internal Sub-Components

Working with peer initiatives such as FAIRCORE4EOSC and guided by their Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)¹⁹, we have identified the set of concepts that play a role in FAIR assessments and related assistance and guidance. These, together with their relationships, are diagrammed in Figure 14 are explained in detail in Deliverable D1.2, as they are not strictly required for interoperability between the OSTrails IFs. These are categorised as “Conceptual” (structured or unstructured narrative), Software, and Data. In addition, there is a higher level of Conceptual object called a “Dimension”, which represents an established principle (e.g. FAIR Principle F1 “(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier”) that motivates the need for the creation of a FAIR test.

Conceptual components describe functionalities and behaviours, Code implements those behaviours, and Data is passed between Code components. The standards selected for each of these FAIR Model components is described in subsequent sections, and it is adherence to these standards that enable the FAIR-IF; the interoperability behaviours of the FAIR-IF are exposed by the Execution component in the middle column of **Figure 14**, where this represents one of the existing FAIR assessment tools.

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv/>

¹⁹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

Figure 14. The components of the FAIR Reference Model

5.2. DCAT Metadata

The FAIR-IF has selected the global standard [DCAT version 3](#) (DCAT3) as its core standard for authoring metadata descriptors for conceptual components. DCAT3 provides most of the metadata fields required to describe the provenance and purpose of a FAIR Testing component (author, title, description, semantic theme, etc.) and is also extensible to allow the addition of new domain-specific facets as required for any given purpose.

Consistent with the extensibility of DCAT3, we have defined the mandatory/optional metadata fields, and any novel fields, in a [DCAT Application Profile](#) (the concept of

Application Profiles has already been covered in detail in [Section 3.2](#)) To the greatest extent possible, the FAIR IF Application Profile (FAIR-IF-AP) adheres to the [DCAT-AP for data portals in Europe](#), ensuring that we are as interoperable as possible with third-party data sources including the [European Data Spaces](#). The FAIR-IF-AP is published as a [series of spreadsheets](#), with commentary about the expected usage of each field, and examples where they are useful. There is an AP for each of the FAIR Reference Model components: FAIR Tests, FAIR Metrics, Benchmarks, and Algorithms.

5.3. OpenAPI interface descriptors

To adhere to the most widely used global standards, all code component interfaces in the FAIR-IF are defined using [version 3 of the OpenAPI Specification](#) (OAS) for Web interface descriptors and defines the input and output for any Web API in a standardised and machine-readable manner. This ensures that all tools in OSTrails can interpret and execute any of the FAIR Testing tools provided by the FAIR-IF in the same way. A detailed description of the OpenAPI standard can be found in [Section 3.3](#).

With respect to deeper issues of interoperability, while the input “signature” for any given test cannot be pre-defined (this problem is discussed in detail in Deliverable D1.2) we have defined what the output model should be for all tests, and this is summarised in the next section.

5.4. Output Data Model

This is the component of the FAIR Reference Model that is most relevant to the FAIR-IF, since it is the only component focused on external interoperability (versus internal interoperability between sub-components). It consists of a Linked Data schema for capturing the output of FAIR Tests and sets of Tests. The FAIR-IF relies on all FAIR assessment (and assistance) tools to adhere to this model to provide interoperability at the level of test result integration. Effectively, different assessment platforms host different FAIR Tests that represent different Metrics and Benchmarks; however, it is possible to execute tests from any of the platforms and merge the results through the shared data model.

The Data Model has been formalised and published as the FAIR Test Results Vocabulary, currently at version 0.0.1 (<https://w3id.org/ftr#>). The current model is depicted in **Figure 15**. Instantiation of these models is achieved using (preferentially) JSON-LD formatted data, consistent with the use of JSON by both the DMP-IF and the SKG-IF, thus also contributing to the Interoperability between the FAIR-IF and other OSTrails IFs.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable introduces the OSTrails reference architecture, and the three Interoperability Frameworks aligned with the project's pillars: Data Management Plans (DMPs), Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), and FAIR Assessment. It provides a comprehensive foundation for enabling interactions between the key components identified in the OSTrails pathways. By specifying standardised interactions within the Interoperability Frameworks and maintaining flexibility for implementation, the architecture ensures adaptability to diverse scenarios. For example, while the reference architecture mandates the use of the DMP API for certain interactions, it allows flexibility in accessing information from data repositories.

A central goal of this work is to avoid vendor lock-in, enabling the seamless interchange of tools and services across typical research workflows. The emphasis on harmonising the modelling and exchange of information across research data management services lays the groundwork for robust and flexible solutions tailored to varied use cases.

The architecture supports both current and emerging interaction patterns, enabling innovative use cases that advance automation and machine-actionability in digital object information exchange. For instance, while it remains uncommon for data repositories to update DMPs, the architecture anticipates and accommodates such scenarios, demonstrating its forward-looking design.

The three interoperability frameworks are not developed in isolation. There are intersections between them. FAIR Assessment serves as a good example of such overlap. The FAIR-IF develops methods to model the results of testing procedures. This information, in turn, can become part of the SKG-IF, such as being linked to a dataset. Similarly, DMPs can incorporate tests for the FAIRness of the datasets they describe.

Whenever pathways indicate that multiple components require similar information from one another, this suggests the need to consider cross-pillar interoperability. For example, FAIR assessment is referenced by all other components within the pathways, as detailed in Chapter 2.

As we continue to develop the commons and refine the interoperability frameworks, we will ensure that the respective data models are semantically aligned, either through a common/shared data model or through mappings that express the equivalences.

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